

EMT Model Validation of an Offshore Wind Power Plant with SGRE DD Wind Turbines under Real Power System Events

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Abstract

Electromagnetic Transient (EMT) models are essential to wind power plant developers and transmission system operators alike. Therefore, during the development of any new Wind Turbines (WTs), EMT models are also developed. These models are quality-assured by validating against measurements from a prototype turbine, specifically for fault ride-through (FRT) cases. One way of performing model validation is through the voltage play-back method described in IEC 61400-21-2, where a voltage-dependent source reproduces the voltage measurements from the site (at the MV terminals of the WT transformer) and the current/power injections from the WT are compared against the measurements (at the LV terminals of the WT transformer). WPPs are designed and developed with the help of these models. However, a WPP electrical system can be complex with wind turbines, passive components, cables, and active components such as filters, Static VAR Compensators, and/or HVDCs. So it is interesting and sometimes essential to ensure that the assessment studies performed during the development of WPP are accurate. Furthermore, passive equipment in the WPP may change important characteristics either due to internal failures or aging, wind turbine control software version, and parameters may be updated, etc. It is often valuable to ensure that models are still capable of representing the actual behaviors seen on the field so that grid compliance and stability can be studied throughout the operation. In this context, this paper presents the EMT model validation of an offshore WPP with Siemens Gamesa Renewable Energy's (SGRE) direct-drive (DD) Type IV Wind Turbines using the voltage play-back method under real power system events. The faults were unbalanced and happened at the nearby grid, leading all the turbines of the plant into FRT mode. The model used was developed during the design of the WPP and the evaluation is done at both the plant and turbine levels. It is shown that the EMT models of operational WPPs were able to reproduce the real measurements with high accuracy. The paper also discusses the different challenges concerning measurement location placement, data acquisition, aggregation methods, preprocessing, turbine connection status, and production at the time of the fault.

1 Introduction

The penetration of large-scale wind power plants (WPPs) and other inverter-based resources (IBRs) is set to increase exponentially in the upcoming decades, driving more complexity into how power systems are designed and operated. During more than 100 years of operation of the traditional power system, the industry has established very robust metrics and modeling techniques for different types of stability and faults based on known boundaries [1]. Nevertheless, due to the current energy transition and ramping-up of IBR penetration, the industry is acknowledging the effects of these devices in several traditional definitions and considering these effects for different stability affects aspects [2]. As a result, more effort is being put into modeling tools as these are becoming more crucial for reliable grid integration and operation of new assets.

Traditionally, system operators and designers have been using root-mean-square (RMS) models for studying the response of the power system to different types of phenomena [3]. Particularly, generator unit and system-level model validation and testing is not a new topic. For decades, TSOs have been

doing model validation using models in the Root-Mean Square (RMS) domain using real power system faults [4, 5]. Thus far, for low levels of IBR penetration, these models offered a good trade-off between accuracy and speed of simulation and were able to represent well the response of synchronous generators [6]. However, as the shares of IBRs get representative in the system, fast control interactions and other phenomena originating from these IBRs cannot be accurately represented by RMS models in some scenarios [7].

In this sense, Electromagnetic Transient (EMT) modeling is becoming increasingly important as it can replicate the electrical characteristics of WPPs with high accuracy in the time domain. Such models often use robust representations of passive equipment (e.g. transformers, cables, generators) and the actual control source code of the turbine and converter, usually embedded in the form of Dynamic Link Libraries (.dlls). During the development of a new Wind Turbine (WT), EMT models are validated against fault ride-through (FRT) site measurements for a wide range of faults and operating points following different standards as IEC 61400-21-1 and

21-2 [8–11]. One of the ways of performing validation against faults is through the so-called voltage play-back method, where a voltage-dependent source reproduces the voltage measurements, and the current injections from the WT are compared against the measurements. These models are then utilized for plant-level studies before connecting to the system.

New standards and definitions such as "IEEE P2800.2 Recommended Practice for Test and Verification Procedures for Inverter-based Resources (IBRs) Interconnecting with Bulk Power Systems" are increasingly looking at utilizing EMT models for continuous assessment of stability and compliance during the operation of WPPs and other resources [7]. During the operation of WPPs, passive equipment in the WPP may change important characteristics either due to internal failures or aging. Furthermore, the control software versions and/or parameters may be changed for different reasons. In this sense, it is important to ensure that models are still capable of representing the actual behaviors seen on the field and that the WPP is still compliant and stable. In this context, the voltage play-back method at different locations of the WPP can be a useful tool. It can not only be used to validate the WT and control models but also the other equipment between the WT and the voltage play-back point.

This paper presents the EMT model validation of an offshore WPP with Siemens Gamesa Renewable Energy's (SGRE) direct-drive (DD) Type IV Wind Turbines using the voltage play-back method under real power system events. The two fault events occurred recently in the neighboring power system of the WPP. Voltage measurements are played back at the plant level. For confidentiality purposes, the names of the plants, locations, and types of wind turbines are omitted and the results are presented in p.u. It is shown that the EMT models of operational WPPs were able to reproduce the real measurements with high accuracy. Different challenges and opportunities concerning such methods are also discussed. Challenges can include selecting suitable events, defining plant topology during the fault, proper tracking of software updates and parameters as well as correct locations for playback, among others. In the following sections, an overview of the model structure and play-back validation procedures are shown, followed by the results and then finally discussions, challenges, and future methodologies are presented to guide future work on the topic.

2 Model Definitions and Validation Methods

The EMT model utilized in this paper is developed in PSCAD™ and includes the permanent magnet synchronous generator (PMSG) along with a full-sized voltage source converter (VSC), commonly referred to as a Type IV wind turbine. The modeled mechanical system of the WTG comprises the aerodynamic and shaft models. Furthermore, the electrical system of the wind turbine consists of the PMSG, full-size back-to-back converter, DC link with the chopper, WTG transformer, and measurement ports. Finally, the control system includes and reduced-order version of the WTG level control and a full-order control for the converter control with actual source code embedded as a .dll (dynamic link library). An

Fig. 1. Setup in the field for fault-ride through tests [10].

overview of the model validation during designs with prototype measurements is first described followed by the description of the play-back method during operation.

2.1 Model Validation During Design

The previously described model has been verified using actual on-site measurements for Fault Ride-Through (FRT) scenarios. Numerous conditions are examined, encompassing a range of grid code parameters, fault types, Short-Circuit Ratio (SCR), retained voltage, power reference, voltage reference, and other operational conditions and parameters. These evaluations are carried out in compliance with various grid codes and standards, such as the IEC 61400-21-1 [8].

Figure (1) illustrates the configuration employed in the field. A wind turbine generator (WTG), filter, and transformer are interconnected with a test unit. Measurements are obtained at multiple points: the low voltage (MP1 - LV) and high voltage (MP2 - HV) sides of the transformer, the short-circuit point (MP3), and the grid side of the test unit (MP4). To conduct on-site measurements, a test unit, known as an FRT container, is employed. This FRT container enables the safe emulation of faults from the perspective of the turbine while minimizing the grid's contribution for safety purposes. The procedure involves reproducing the measured voltages at MP2 as an equivalent voltage source in the PSCAD environment to validate the models, as depicted in Figure (2). The model's response at MP1 is then compared to the measured data.

Illustrated below is an instance of a three-phase fault scenario, where the power reference is set at 0.25 p.u. and the voltage reference at 1 p.u. Measurements were taken at the LV MP1 side. The comparison between field measurements and PSCAD simulation results is presented in Figure (3). The upper graph displays the three-phase LV voltages, while the three-phase LV currents in RMS are depicted separately. The PSCAD simulations exhibit a close alignment with the field measurements, indicating the high accuracy of the models in accurately representing real-world conditions. This validation process is replicated for numerous fault scenarios, ensuring comprehensive verification of the model. In addition to field

Fig. 2. Voltage Play-back at turbine level.

Fig. 3 Model validation and comparison of the three-phase RMS voltages and currents for a 3ph fault between the prototype turbine at the field and PSCAD [11].

testing, the industry is making progress in component and sub-system testing, as well as implementing Hardware/Software-in-the-loop real-time solutions [12–15]. It is foreseeable that the current model validation procedures, which are already widely adopted, will continue to evolve, leading to further enhancements in accuracy and reliability.

2.2 Model Validation During Operation - Voltage Play-back

For performing model validation with field measurements on operational WPPs, the procedure is similar but the measurement devices and location differ. The field voltage and current waveforms are sampled using ELSPEC™ at 1024 samples per cycle, which allows for very accurate measurements. Some turbines are equipped with such devices at MP1 and ELSPECs are also installed on the plant level. The play-back procedure in this paper uses the aggregated model where a number of turbines are connected to an equivalent PI Section representing the

Fig. 4 Voltage Play-back at plant level in the offshore substation point.

array cables as shown in Figure (4). The voltage is stepped-up for transmission through the export cable. At this point, a measurement point at the plant level is located and used for playing back the voltage.

3 Results

In this section, two faults are presented and several aspects of model validation are explored. All figures are presented in p.u. and calculated using the base for either the WT or the plant. The sequence components are calculated based on IEC 61400-21-1 method [8]. The play-back was realized according to Figure (4) at the plant level. All the turbines are operating in PV mode, i.e. they operate with fixed active power and voltage references. Furthermore, the active power post-fault is limited to 90 % of the pre-fault for 0.5 seconds. In the cases presented below, all the turbines were mostly operating with the same voltage reference. A summary of the two faults is given below:

- Fault A: This fault occurred at a time when all turbines were connected and producing similarly close to rated active power, therefore the plant level production was close to 1 p.u.
- Fault B: This fault happened during a time when the turbines were producing a wide variation of active power, from 0.7 p.u. up to 1 p.u. Additionally, some wind turbines on the cluster were already disconnected prior to the fault for maintenance, resulting in a total plant production of around 0.68 p.u.

Although play-back was always performed at plant-level MP in Figure (4), the comparison for each case is done at either the turbine or plant levels to illustrate a specific discussion.

3.1 Validation against Fault A

The turbine level validation for Fault A can be observed in Figure (5). The PSCAD model was able to reproduce with high accuracy all the stages of the fault, including minor oscillations. Zoomed-in sub-figures on the right-hand side show high accuracy even at the transient periods of fault-inception and fault-clearing. Due to all turbines being connected and

Fig. 5. Fault A - All turbines producing similar power - Validation for WTG Level.

producing similar power, despite the wide geographical variation of the wind turbines, the model validation for Fault A is straightforward.

Minor differences can be observed and expected in the reactive current and power as well as for the positive sequence active current during fault-clearing. Different components in the WPP have frequency-dependent components and non-linearity such as saturation. Furthermore, the actual impedance of cables and transformers often differs slightly from what the datasheet offers due to tolerances. These dependencies are very difficult to model with high accuracy, despite best efforts.

3.2 Validation against Fault B

Figure (6) shows the validation for Fault B. Three different comparisons are performed to validate the model and are presented in sub-figures (6 - a), (6 - b) and (6 - c).

- For the case in sub-figure (a), a comparison at one specific WTG is done. The power production of this specific turbine was considered the same for all the turbines and the original model with all the turbines connected was used, despite in reality they were all producing different powers and some turbines were disconnected in reality. This yielded a higher power production on the plant level than in reality. However, at the turbine level, it is possible to observe that the model is able to replicate very well the positive sequence active current and negative sequence reactive current as the pre-fault conditions between the model and field measurements match. On the other hand, for positive sequence reactive current, the model has an offset of the reactive current since in reality not all turbines are producing 0.9 p.u. and some are disconnected.

Nonetheless, it is still possible to see that the dynamics are quite similar despite the offset.

- In sub-figure (b) a comparison at plant-level is performed instead. The total active power production of the aggregated turbines was matched with the total plant production at the time of the fault of around 0.68 p.u. In this case, the original model was also used and the disconnected turbines were not removed from the aggregation. It can be observed that the reactive currents in both positive and negative sequences are relatively similar in both cases. However, the ramp-up rate for the active power is different for the simulation and the plant level in case (b). This can be explained by the fact that not all turbines are connected nor produce the same power, therefore each turbine will have a different time to reach 90% of the pre-fault power.
- Finally, in sub-figure (c), another comparison at plant-level is done. This time differently than in sub-figure (b), the turbines disconnected were removed from the aggregation and the total power of the remaining turbines was equally divided again. This time, the ramp-up rate behaved better as the correct number of turbines at the time of the fault were considered on the model.

4 Discussions, Challenges and Future Methodologies

The two validation test cases presented in the previous section highlight important factors that need to be taken into account when performing play-back in plant-level validation. In this section, important considerations regarding the models and validation procedures are discussed.

Fig. 6. Fault B - Turbines producing different power and some disconnected - Comparison for WTG and Plant Level.

4.1 Challenges for Play-back at Turbine Level During Operation

A question that may arise often is why not perform play-back at turbine level. This is technically possible and done nowadays as shown by model validation during turbine design testing campaigns. However, in the current way measurement devices are installed on operational WPPs, leveraging the measurements already taken for voltage and current for the converter control, it is not possible to perform play-back at the turbine level.

This is mainly due to the fact that the turbine controls obtain the voltage and current reference signals from the output of the WT after the converter reactor and filter, on the LV side. This is the same place where the measurement devices are installed, therefore the play-back cannot be performed on top of where the converter takes the reference and instead needs to be done at the MV side, where measurements are not done on operational turbines. Play-back techniques at this point could be explored in the future but several pre-processing steps would be required.

4.2 Concerning Production Level and Turbine Status at Time of Fault

As mentioned in the results section, it is crucial to obtain the pre-fault operating points at the plant and individual turbine levels, as these are information used to initialize the model before the fault. If an aggregated model is used, the reactive power especially can be expected to deviate as the capabilities change depending on the production level of the WTGs individually on-site. Furthermore, the pre-fault turbine connection

status needs to be verified before performing the validation. The simplest play-back would be when all turbines are connected and producing similar power at the time of the fault. If that is not the case, the aggregate model should be modified in order to only account for turbines that were connected at the moment of the fault, as shown for Fault B.

As verified, when operating points deviate significantly among turbines and/or turbines are disconnected prior to the fault, the play-back procedure on the plant level becomes relatively more complex. Ideally, for model validation, a fault similar to Fault A should be selected, where conditions are more favorable. However, in most scenarios, it is unlikely that at the time of faults, all turbines will be connected and produce the exact same amount. Therefore, small deviations can be expected when performing validation of large complex sites. In this case, the validation may take place at a smaller part of the network, e.g. turbine-level, array of turbines, or cluster of arrays. This is certainly dependent on the measurement availability.

4.3 Aggregated Models vs Full-Order Turbine Representation

Aggregated model representations of a WPP at the plant, cluster, or array levels are known to be suitable for different grid compliance and stability studies during design and are often used by designers for WPP studies. Hybrid models, where one of the turbine arrays is represented in detail without aggregation and the rest of the WPP as aggregated, are also used in some cases to perform further studies on the turbine level

but still keep a lower computational burden for the simulation. In this paper, a fully aggregated model at the plant level was used to perform the play-back and model validation. However, other types of aggregations done at the array or cluster levels instead of the plant level could allow for a better representation of the active power injection and therefore more accurate reactive power injection.

Full-order models without any aggregation can offer more accurate results and be able to capture any eventual disconnection of turbines during the event. Disconnecting turbines during the event is not possible in an aggregated model. However, such detailed models can be computationally heavier and much more complex to parameterize with precision as the pre-fault operating points of every turbine would need to be obtained.

When selecting a suitable representation for model validation of an operational wind power plant, it is important to take these aspects into account. If the highest fidelity possible is required during model validation, full-order models could offer flexibility for parameterization and topology modification.

5 Conclusion

This paper introduces the utilization of the voltage play-back method for validating EMT (Electromagnetic Transient) models during the operation of Wind Power Plants (WPPs). As the number of large-scale WPPs and other inverter-based resources (IBRs) increases, there is a growing need to continuously assess and ensure the stability and compliance of these resources throughout the operation. To continuously assess that, the paper shows that quality-assured EMT models validated using prototype turbines during design can accurately represent the real behaviors observed in the field after years of operation.

The voltage play-back method at plant-level is proposed as a useful tool for validating the WT (Wind Turbine) and control models, as well as other equipment within the WPP. The method involves playing back voltage measurements from real fault events that occurred near the WPP. By comparing the EMT models' reproduction of the current and power measurements with high accuracy, the paper demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed approach and the accuracy of the models developed during the design phase of a new WT. Several challenges associated with the voltage play-back method are also discussed. These challenges may include selecting suitable events, defining the plant topology during the fault in terms of aggregation and turbines involved, tracking software updates and parameters correctly, and determining appropriate locations for play-back. These considerations are essential for ensuring the validity and reliability of the validation process.

Moving forward, as the quantity and size of WPPs are increasing in the power system, EMT model validation for continuous assessment of grid compliance and stability will be more and more necessary. The learnings of this paper can be valuable for drafting guidelines on how to assess the accuracy of the models given a specific scenario at which the event being used happened.

6 Legal Disclaimer

Figures and values presented in this paper should not be used to judge the performance of Siemens Gamesa Renewable Energy technology as they are solely presented for demonstration purpose. Any opinions or analysis contained in this paper are the opinions of the authors and not necessarily the same as those of Siemens Gamesa Renewable Energy.

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